

IMPACT OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 ON MULNIVASI BAHUJAN SOCIETY

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Abstract:

While the implementation of the educational policies or thoughts of Father of the Nation Jyotirao Phule, Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj and Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar is essential for National Development in the 21st century, the National Educational policy 2020 has been passed to enslave the Mulnivasi Bahujan Society in this country by removing their educational policy. The present research paper has briefly highlighted the impact of this policy on the Mulnivasi Bahujan Society.

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Objective of Research:

1. To study the relevance of the Educational thoughts of Father of the Nation Jyotirao Phule, Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj and Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar.
2. To Review of National Education Policy 2020.
3. To study the impact of National Education policy 2020 on the Mulnivasi Bahujan Society.

Hypothesis of Research:

1. The National Educational policy 2020 is based on a New Economic Policy 1991 that is inconsistent with the Indian Constitution.

National Education Policy 2020:

National Education Policy: By ending 10 + 2 in school education, a new system of 5 + 3+ 3 + 4 will be implemented. On Wednesday (July 29, 2020), the Modi Cabinet approved a new education policy. This national education policy was drafted during the first term of Prime Minister Modi. But the policy had been stalled for the last two to three years. This education has been brought to bring about a complete change in life.

The Modi government at the center has approved a new education policy. From the Ministry of Manpower Development. A new education policy was drafted under the chairmanship of Dr. Kasturirangan. In addition, the Ministry of Human Resource Development was renamed the Ministry of Education. The first education policy was implemented in the country in 1986. This education policy was later changed in 1992. The Right to Education Act was introduced in 2009 and has been in force since 2013. Completely abolish the format of 10+2 under the new education policy

It is now divided into 10+ 2 and 5 +3 +3 +4 formats. That means now In the first phase i.e. in the first five years - three years of pre-primary and classes I to II will be imparted. The first five years of school will include pre-primary school

and three years of foundation phase, Class 1 and Class II

In The second stage -next three years will be divided into 3rd to 5th grade preparation stages.

In the third stage - Intermediate three years (classes 6 to 8) and

In the fourth stage - four years in the secondary stage (classes 9 to 12). In addition to this, students can now take the desired courses in arts, commerce and science in schools.

Some points of the new education policy.

1. The importance of board exams will decrease
2. NCERT Curriculum: For the first time, a curriculum will be decided for pre-primary school. The course will be applicable to all pre-primary schools in the country. NCERT will decide the course. Preference should be given to education up to the fifth standard in the mother tongue.
3. Emphasis on vocational curriculum
4. The school report card will be changed
5. Big changes in higher education
6. Regulators of higher education throughout the country
7. New Education Commission

Some other important aspects of the new education policy

By 2040, all higher education institutions will have to create multi-subject institutions with more than 3000 students.

By 2030, there will be at least one major higher multi-subject institution in each district.

The curriculum of the institutions should be such that emphasis should be laid on the development of public institutions.

Institutions will have the option of running open distance learning and online programs.

All types of deemed and related universities created for higher education will only now be known as universities.

The goal will be to develop the intellectual, social, physical, emotional and moral abilities of human beings together.

Impact of National Education Policy 2020 on Mulnivasi Bahujan Society:

According to this policy, there will be a group of 10 to 20 schools and this group will be controlled by a separate system. The existing 800 universities, 40,000 colleges will be converted into about 15,000 higher institutions. Large investments will be made in the public sector to expand and revive education. Education is the basis of life. Therefore, the Constitution of India will provide fundamental rights to the Mulnivasi Bahujan Society, which has been kept away from education for years, and will involve them in the development process from January 26, 1950. Today, their fundamental rights are being taken away from through the National Education Policy 2020. The policy does not make special provisions for the development of socially and educationally backward sections. The policy aims to ensure that not everyone gets free and compulsory education. This policy openly adopts market oriented education system without considering the education of the lowest level Mulnivasi Bahujan Society. Therefore, adopting the educational thinking policy of Father of the Nation Jyotirao Phule, Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj and Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar are essential for the progress of the Mulnivasi Bahujan Society.

Reference:

Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government Of India

Loksatta.com, MaharashtraTimes.com